

ISic3708

I.Sicily inscription 3708

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

cippus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Rosolini

Provenance

contrada Stafenna, found October 1972 during agricultural work

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Rosolini

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI330109

1. [Α] μπλις
2. [χ] ρηστὸς
3. [κ] αὶ ἄμε-
4. νπτος
5. [ἐ]ζησ-
6. [ε]ν ἔτ η
7. γ'.
- 8.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

PHI 330109

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 26.1117

Agnello, S.L. 1972-1973. Cippo con iscrizione funeraria da Stafenna. *Archivio Storico Siracusano*. 2: 99-102.

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